

Diffuse Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopic Study of Chemical Bonding and Hydrothermal Stability of an Aminosilane on Metal Oxide Surfaces

S. Naviroj, J. L. Koenig, H. Ishida

Department of Macromolecular Science, Case Western Reserve University, Cleveland, Ohio 44106, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy is used to study the metal oxide/silane interfaces. Structures of γ -aminopropyltrimethylethoxysilane (γ -APDMES) coupling agent depends on the surface characteristics of the substrate. The amine group of the silane molecule forms a hydrogen bond with the silica surface. Due to the more positively charged surface of aluminum oxide, the amine group is repelled from the surface forming a free or non-hydrogen bonded amine. The infrared frequencies of Al-O-Si and Ti-O-Si asymmetric stretching modes are calculated to be 958 and 921 cm^{-1} respectively. By using the diffuse reflectance infrared technique, these Metal-O-Si bonds are detected at 963 and 1030 cm^{-1} for the alumina and titania samples, respectively, which agree favorably with the calculated frequencies. When the treated metal oxide powders are immersed in 80°C water, the desorption of silane is more rapid when aluminum powder, rather than titanium powder, is the substrate. Silica powder, however, forms a more hydrophobic surface. The rate of silane desorption decreased in the order of aluminum oxide, titanium oxide and silicon oxide.

INTRODUCTION

The surface composition of glasses and the surface treatment can affect the performance of the fiber reinforced plastics. Heat treatment, additives, etching, surface leaching are often used in the commercial production process to improve the durability, hardness, chemical resistance and adhesion. The chemical analysis of the surface is essential to understand the nature of these effects.

Various techniques were employed in order to obtain the chemical analysis of the surface. Difficulties often arise due to the sensitivity of the technique. The isolation of the surface property from the bulk property has proven to be tedious or difficult in many cases. The characterization of glass/epoxy and glass/silane interfaces was reported by using ion scattering spectroscopy (ISS) and secondary ion mass spectroscopy (SIMS) (1). When the ion sputtering technique was used on an incompletely cured silane coating, the SIMS spectra at different depths of penetration revealed that within a region of 250Å of the glass silane interface, three interphase domains exist. Auger Electron Spectroscopy (AES), a surface technique, was used to obtain the composition of

glass (2). This technique provides the depth profile information of the first 10 - 50Å of the surface. In order to understand the nature of the chemical interaction on the surface of glass, it is necessary to use techniques which can yield information about molecular structure. Shih and Koenig (3) showed that the Raman spectroscopy could be used to characterize silane coupling agents in the bulk, in aqueous solution and on glass fiber surfaces. When a coupling agent was applied to glass fibers from aqueous solution, vinylpoly-siloxane polymer was found by Raman spectroscopy to be chemically bonded to the glass surface (4). Chiang (5) used solid state ¹³C NMR to characterize the structure of a silane coupling agent on glass fiber surface. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy was used by Moses (6) to observe the reaction of alkylamine-silane with metal oxide electrode. Several bonding schemes were found to be possible on metal oxide surfaces.

Infrared spectroscopy is widely used to study the molecular structure and chemical composition of surfaces (7,8). The classical infrared transmission method provides both qualitative and quantitative data of the surface species (9) and has been extensively employed. With the development of Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and improvement of the signal-to-noise ratio, several methods of infrared spectroscopy were successfully employed to obtain spectra. The reflection-absorption technique showed that the molecular structure of silane treated on metal substrates could be obtained (10). Recent work by Yoshida and Ishida (11) typifies that the reflection-absorption technique can also provide information on molecular orientation of surface species on metal substrates. The attenuated total reflection (ATR) technique has been used to study the silane interface (12). Crystalline Al₂O₃ was used as a substrate. The extent of hydrolysis and cross-linking of silane layers were studied by this technique.

The diffuse reflectance technique was developed many years ago (13,14). This technique uses the scattering property of the sample. The scattered light is collected by mirrors and transmitted to a detector. The basic principles of this technique were developed by Kabelka and Munk (13) in 1931. The sample is placed in a sample pan and the spectrum is ratioed with a pure KBr spectrum. The unit of absorption is the Kabelka-Munk unit which has the relationship as shown below.

$$f(R_{\infty}) = (1 - R_{\infty})^2 / 2R_{\infty}$$

where: R_{∞} is the absolute reflectance of the layer

The spectral information depends on the particle size and the scattering coefficient. Qualitative information can be obtained easily; however, quantitative information is ambiguous at high concentrations (15). To perform an accurate spectral subtraction, Kabelka-Munk units of components to be subtracted must be low (16). The sample may be diluted with KCl or KBr powder. Some of the advantages in using the diffuse reflectance technique are that it requires no sample preparation, and the unperturbed structure of the molecules adsorbed on the surface can be studied. The conventional sample preparation method where KBr powder is ground with the sample and pressed into a pellet is completely avoided in the diffuse reflectance technique. In the diffuse reflectance method, a sample can be examined directly with or without dilution with KBr powder.

In fiber reinforced plastic technology, glass fibers or other types of fillers are used to provide either strength or as an extender to the material. The technology has advanced tremendously in the past decade. The essence of understanding molecular bonding at the surface of glass fibers or fillers is indispensable for the improved technology. Since glass fibers are composed of various metal oxides, it is essential to elucidate the role of these metal oxides on the structure of the silanes. With different types of oxides present in glass fibers, the aminosilane can react differently toward these metal oxides. Each oxide has its own intrinsic characteristics such as surface isoelectric point (17). Aminosilanes have been used in fiber reinforced plastic technology. Extensive research on its molecular structure reveals that this compound can form many structures depending on the pH of the treating solution and also the drying conditions (18). Hence, the structure of aminosilanes may be especially

vulnerable to the microheterogeneity of the surface. The key to good mechanical performance and efficient processing of composite systems lies in the properties of the filler/resin interface. The physical and chemical states of the filler surface strongly affect the nature, type, concentration, orientation, and the distribution of silane on the surface.

When silane is applied on the surface, it can chemisorb, physisorb, and cross-polymerize. The metal-oxide-silane (M-O-Si) bond is believed to be partly responsible for the coupling stability.

In this paper we will characterize the surface of treated metal oxides by using transmission and diffuse reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. Immersion test will show what type of surface will be more hydrolytically stable in hot water. The results will provide a mechanistic understanding of how the surface of reinforcements and an aminosilane interact. In order to obtain information about the hydrothermal stability of the interfacial bonds, we have chosen a monoalkoxy silane.

Experimental

Aluminum oxide, titanium oxide, and silica powders with a specific surface area of 130, 100, and 50 m²/g respectively, were kindly supplied by Mr. Lierson of Degussa, Inc. γ -Aminopropyltrimethylethoxysilane (γ -APDMES) was purchased from Petrarch Systems Inc. and used as received. One percent and 0.2% by weight of γ -APDMES was hydrolyzed in deionized distilled water for 40 min. Metal oxide powder was immersed in the solution for 15 min. The retrieval of the powder was made by centrifuging, and the solution was decanted. The treated powder was dried in air at room temperature for one day and heated in 80°C for one day. Immersion test was made by placing the treated powder in 80°C distilled water. The powder was retrieved from the water at various intervals for infrared analysis.

The amount of γ -APDMES was calibrated by transmission infrared technique. γ -APDMES was allowed to hydrolyze by absorbing moisture from air for three weeks. The surface of the sample was scratched at several occasions to ensure complete exposure to moist air. The dried sample was carefully weighed with a Perkin Elmer microbalance with the accuracy of ± 0.0001 mg. The weighed sample was ground with KBr powder and compressed into a pellet for infrared analysis.

A Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (Digilab FTS-20E) was used to obtain the spectral information. The spectrometer was constantly purged with dry nitrogen. A nitrogen cooled Mercury Cadmium Telluride (MCT) detector was used for high sensitivity data collection. A Digilab DRA-100 diffuse reflectance accessory with hemispherical mirrors was placed in the sample chamber and used to collect the diffusely scattered light from the sample. To improve the signal-to-noise ratio, long scanning period of 600 scans was utilized at resolution 4 cm⁻¹ but in many instances 200 scans were sufficient.

The calibration of powders were done by carefully weighing the powder with a microbalance. The weighed powders were ground with approximately 200 mg of KBr powder and pressed into a pellet. The transmission infrared technique was used to monitor the intensity of the intrinsic peaks due to the powders versus the weight in milligrams of the powders.

Preparation of sample for the diffuse reflectance spectroscopy only requires diluting the sample with KBr powder. No grinding was applied during the preparation. The single beam spectrum of the sample was ratioed with a single beam spectrum of pure KBr powder. Through mathematical manipulation, the spectrum has a Kabelka-Munk unit.

RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the diffuse reflectance spectra of silicon oxide, titanium oxide, and aluminum oxide powders. The choice of these powders in this experiment is justified by the fact that silica is a major component in glass fibers. Titanium and aluminum powders were used since the surface charges of these powders are different from silica and cover a wide pH range. Therefore, the surface charge effect may be observed. Another reason for choosing titanium and aluminum oxide powders is the nature of the infrared absorption of these powders. From fig. 1B and 1C, it can be seen that these two powders do not

Figure 1. Diffuse reflectance infrared spectra of
 A) silica B) titanium oxide C) aluminum oxide

The absence of infrared absorption in the region between 1600 and 800 cm^{-1} of titanium and aluminum oxides facilitates the study of aminosilane compound which has infrared adsorption around 1600 cm^{-1} .

absorb in the region of interest where the silane coupling agent absorbs the infrared light. Aminosilane coupling agent has major adsorption bands from 1600 to 900 cm^{-1} . The region around 1600 cm^{-1} yields information concerning the amine group. The band around 1000 cm^{-1} is informative about the siloxane bond and perhaps the Metal-O-Si bond. The peak at 3750 cm^{-1} in fig. 1 is due to the free surface silanol of silica powder (19). The band at 1058 cm^{-1} is due to the Si-O-Si stretching mode of silica. This region overlaps with the Si-O-Si stretching mode of the silane coupling agent itself. Titanium oxide (fig. 1B) has a strong band at 700 cm^{-1} whereas aluminum oxide (fig. 1C) has a strong absorbance at 830 cm^{-1} .

Figure 2. Diffuse reflectance infrared spectra of
 A) treated silica with 1% γ -APDMES by weight
 B) untreated silica
 C) the digital subtracted spectrum of A-B.

Figure 2 shows the difference spectrum of the treated silica powder (fig. 2A) minus the untreated powder (fig. 2B). The subtracted spectrum reveals information about the surface treatment and the possible chemical changes that may occur. From the difference spectrum (fig. 2C), the peak at 1596 cm^{-1} is assigned to the NH_2 deformation mode of the silane coupling agent molecule. A weak band at 1412 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 1257 cm^{-1} are due to the asymmetric and symmetric deformation modes of SiCH_3 respectively.

Figure 3. The difference spectrum (C) of
 A) treated titanium oxide and
 B) untreated titanium oxide
 reveals the structure of γ -APDMES adsorbed onto the surface.

Figure 3A is the spectrum of titanium oxide treated with γ -APDMES. Figure 3B is the spectrum of titanium oxide wetted with distilled water and dried. Difference spectrum of titanium oxide treated with silane (fig. 3C) shows a band at 1635 cm^{-1} . This band together with a broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} (not shown in fig. 3) are due to the vibration modes of water molecules on the sample. The NH_2 band is noticeable. The location of the NH_2 deformation band of the treated titanium oxide sample shifted downward from 1596 cm^{-1} , in the case of silica, to 1584 cm^{-1} . The band at 1058 cm^{-1} is assigned to the Si-O-Si antisymmetric stretching mode (20). The presence of this band means that coupling agent dimers are present on the surface. The relative intensity of this dimer peak with 1257 cm^{-1} peak is

comparatively low compared to the spectrum of the condensed dimers of the hydrolyzate of γ -APDMES (21). Another peak is observed at 1030 cm^{-1} . With the presence of this 1030 cm^{-1} band, the low intensity of the dimer peak at 1058 cm^{-1} is justified. Some of γ -APDMES molecules may condense and form dimers while some of the remaining molecules may form a chemical bond to the titanium oxide surface. With the presence of 1030 cm^{-1} band and the lower intensity of the dimer peak at 1058 cm^{-1} , the band at 1030 cm^{-1} is tentatively assigned to the surface bonding of titanium and silane coupling agent (Ti-O-Si).

Figure 4. Diffuse reflectance infrared spectra of
 A) γ -APDMES treated aluminum oxide
 B) untreated aluminum oxide
 C) the difference spectrum.

Figure 4A and fig. 4B are the spectra of γ -APDMES treated and distilled-water-wetted samples of aluminum oxides, respectively. The difference spectrum of treated aluminum powder (fig. 4C) shows a peak at 1575 cm^{-1} . This peak can be assigned to the NH_2 deformation mode. The frequency of this peak is now at 1575 cm^{-1} as compared to 1596 cm^{-1} for silica and 1584 cm^{-1} for titanium oxide samples. A peak at 1058 cm^{-1} which was assigned to the Si-O-Si stretching mode of silane is present along with a new peak at 963 cm^{-1} . Again the relative intensity of the dimer (Si-O-Si) peak at 1058 cm^{-1} is lower compared to the condensed dimer of the γ -APDMES hydrolyzate. The same argument can be used to explain the appearance of the 963 cm^{-1} peak. The presence of the 963 cm^{-1} peak and the lower intensity of the 1058 cm^{-1} peak lead to the tentative assignment of the 963 cm^{-1} band to be due to the surface reaction of silane and aluminum oxide surface (Al-O-Si).

Figure 5. Transmission infrared spectrum of
 A) untreated aluminum oxide
 B) treated aluminum oxide with γ -APDMES.

The peak at 1258 cm^{-1} due to SiCH_3 is used as an indication of the amount of silane present on the surface.

The powders treated with 1% γ -APDMES by weight were immersed in distilled water at 80°C . It was observed that aluminum samples sank immediately in the hot water whereas slight difficulties were experienced with the titanium oxide powder and required more than 20 min. before immersion. The treated silicon oxide, however, did not immerse even when vigorous agitation was applied. Figure 5 shows the infrared transmission spectra of untreated aluminum oxide (fig. 5A) and the treated (fig. 5B) samples. The small peak at 1257 cm^{-1} , due to the SiCH_3 groups, is used as an indication of the amount of silane remaining on the surface of the powder after immersion in 80°C water. The peak at 830 cm^{-1} is used as the internal thickness band. With the calibration curves of γ -APDMES and powder, the amount of γ -APDMES present per milligram of oxide powder can be plotted versus immersion time as shown in fig. 6. It can be seen that silane treated on aluminum powder desorbs at a much faster rate than on the titanium sample.

The stability of the interfacial bond between silane and metal oxide surface is an important factor in the hydrothermal stability of composite materials. Water can hydrolyze the oxane bond and sever the interfacial linkage. To study the interfacial bond, metal oxide powders were treated with 0.2% by weight of γ -APDMES. The amount of silane coupling agent adsorbed on the powder surface of the sample before immersion test was calculated by using the transmission infrared technique. The same sample was also examined by using the diffuse reflectance

Figure 6. Desorption curve of γ -APDMES.

The number of γ -APDMES molecules remaining on the powder per milligram of powder is plotted as a function of immersion time.

infrared technique. The samples that were retrieved from the immersion test were all examined by the diffuse reflectance technique. The amount of silane present on the powder surface can be calculated by relating the diffuse reflectance spectrum with the transmission spectrum of the sample before the immersion test.

Figure 7.

Desorption curve of γ -APDMES at low coverage on silica, titanium oxide, and aluminum oxide powders.

The treated powders were immersed in 80°C distilled water. All three powders immersed easily in the water, unlike the previous case where silica treated with 1% γ -APDMES did not immerse. The powders were recovered at various intervals for infrared examination. The plot in Figure 7 shows the comparison of the desorption of γ -APDMES from three different powders. It can be seen that aluminum oxide loses silane molecules at the fastest rate whereas silica maintains silane molecules the longest.

It was also observed that γ -APDMES does not adsorb very strongly onto the aluminum oxide surface when compared with titanium oxide or silica. The low adsorption may be influenced by the surface isoelectric point (IEP) of aluminum oxide which is 9.1. The surface of aluminum oxide in silane solution is near neutral and there is no strong interaction of silane to the aluminum oxide surface. However, silica, which has IEP=2.2, is more negatively charged in the silane solution. Strong interaction of amine group of the silane molecule may exist with silica. Therefore, a higher adsorption of silane is observed with silica sample.

DISCUSSION

The appearance of the peak at 965 cm^{-1} in the difference spectrum of silane treated aluminum was tentatively assigned to the Al-O-Si stretching mode. The frequency of Al-O-Si stretching mode can be calculated by a simple harmonic oscillator model where the nuclei represent a point mass and the bonding force between nuclei represents a spring constant according to Hook's law (20).

The calculated frequency of Al-O-Si at 958 cm^{-1} agrees well with that observed in fig. 4. When digital subtraction was performed, the reference (untreated) sample was first wetted with distilled water and dried. The reason for doing so is to eliminate the difference due to dry and wet samples as well as the possible artifact. It was observed that dry and wet-then-dry samples without silane are different. When these two untreated samples were subtracted, a peak around 960 cm^{-1} appeared along with the water peak at 1640 cm^{-1} . The same observation was made with dried and wet-then-dry titanium samples. Hence, extreme caution must be taken to interpret the band in this frequency range.

Ishida *et al* (21) showed that the SiCH_3 band at 1255 cm^{-1} had a slightly lower intensity than the dimer (Si-O-Si) peak at 1058 cm^{-1} of the hydrolyzate of γ -APDMES. With the observation of the lowering in intensity of dimer peak at 1058 cm^{-1} compared with SiCH_3 peak at 1258 cm^{-1} plus an appearance of 963 cm^{-1} band, the band at 963 cm^{-1} can therefore be assigned to the Al-O-Si antisymmetric stretching mode. When the sample is rinsed with THF, the dimers, which are not chemically bonded to the surface, can be washed away. The reduction in intensity

of 1058 cm^{-1} peak is the consequence of the dimer desorption. This evidence indicates that silane coupling agent forms a chemical bond on the aluminum surface. Similar calculations can be made for the titanium oxide sample. The observed band at 1030 cm^{-1} is the closest to the calculated band at 921 cm^{-1} and is tentatively assigned to the Ti-O-Si band.

The surface charge may have an influence on the orientation of the silane molecule adsorbed on the surface. The degree of surface charge can be determined by the isoelectric point (IEP). IEP is determined by the pH at which the surface will be neutral. Silica, titanium oxide and aluminum oxide have IEP of 2.2, 6.0, and 9.1 respectively (17). A cationic silane such as γ -APDMES can have an interaction with the surface through the amine group at the end of the propyl chain. In the difference spectra of treated powders, the positions of an amine deformation are different. Spectrum of treated aluminum powder (fig. 4C) shows a peak at 1575 cm^{-1} . This peak was assigned to the free amine or non-hydrogen bonded amine. Spectrum of treated silica shows a peak at 1596 cm^{-1} . The shifting of an amine deformation peak to a higher frequency means that amine is hydrogen bonded (22,23). It should be noted that an unheat-treated sample usually shows the amine deformation band at 1575 cm^{-1} due to the aminebicarbonate salt. Since the sample has been heat treated and the characteristic bicarbonate band at 1330 cm^{-1} is absent, the aminebicarbonate salt is out of consideration. Illustrated in fig. 3C is the amine deformation frequency of treated titanium oxide sample at 1584 cm^{-1} . Spectroscopic evidence indicates that the conformation of the silane molecule is different on different metal oxide surfaces. The structures of γ -APDMES on metal oxide surfaces are proposed in fig. 8.

Figure 8.

Proposed structures of γ -APDMES on the surface of silica, titanium oxide, and aluminum powders.

Tertykh *et al* (24) reported that aminoorganosilyl groups form strong hydrogen bonds with the residual surface OH groups. Vacuum conditioning of aminoorganosilicas at $400 - 450^\circ\text{C}$ leads to removal of most hydroxyl groups, and consequently, to a breakdown of hydrogen bonding. According to the proposed structures in fig. 8, the silane adsorbed on silica surface bends down and forms a hydrogen bond with the surface.

Since the IEP of silica is 2.2, it means that the surface has a large excess of negative charge at the natural pH of the aminosilane solution. The amine may preferentially adsorb onto these sites. On the other hand, aluminum oxide has IEP of 9.1 and the surface is nearly neutral in the silane solution. When the silane molecule adsorbs onto the near neutral surface, no strong surface attraction exists. When the 1% silane-treated powders were put into a vial of 80°C water, aluminum powder sank very easily into the water. Titanium powder did not sink as easily as aluminum oxide powder, and treated silica did not sink at all. It can be explained from the proposed structures that the propyl chain of the silane molecule created a hydrophobic surface on the silica surface. Treated aluminum oxide sank readily because of the free amine group which interacts with the surrounding water and helps in dispersion of powder in water. When the powders were treated at a low concentration, treated silica powder, along with titanium and aluminum oxides, immersed easily in 80°C water. With low coverage of approximately 0.5 monolayer, silica surface is not completely covered with silane molecules. The exposed surface can interact with water during immersion and the powder dispersed easily in water.

Immersion test shows that desorption of silane is more rapid in the case of aluminum oxide powder than titanium oxide powder. Two major causes can be considered. First, the hydrophilicity of the treated aluminum oxide surface helps water to interact quickly with the silane. However, the equilibrium of water

penetration into the silane layers may be reached quickly since the thickness of the silane is at most a few layers. Second, the hydrothermal stability of various Si-O-M bond may be different. In fact, the latter cause may be more dominant in this case. For the practical application in FRP industry, the composition of glass fibers may be important in designing hydrothermally stable materials. The contribution of different amounts of metal oxide changes the IEP of the material, therefore can change the conformation of the silane molecules at the interface.

It is not clear whether microheterogeneity exists on the glass fiber surface. However, the various M-O-Si bonds at the interface are likely to have different hydrothermal stability. The weaker bonds may be preferentially hydrolyzed. The hydrolyzed bonds yield hydrolysis which function as driving forces for further water collection creating water pockets. The water pockets impose a strong osmotic pressure on surrounding chains, reducing the hydrothermal stability due to the mechanochemical mechanism and eventually leads to catastrophic failure of the silane.

CONCLUSIONS

Diffuse reflectance FT-IR spectroscopy was used to study the structure of γ -APDMES on metal oxide surfaces. The structure of silane depends on the substrate. Silane on silica forms a cyclic structure in which the amine group bends down and forms a hydrogen bond with the surface. Alumina, on the other hand, has less surface attraction and thus forms a free or non-hydrogen bonded amine. The silanol group of γ -APDMES can form a chemical bond with the metal oxide surface. Infrared bands around 963 cm^{-1} for the interfacial Al-O-Si bond and at 1030 cm^{-1} for the interfacial Ti-O-Si bond were observed. Immersion experiments show different hydrophobicity of the 1% silane-treated metal oxide surfaces. The treated silica repels water and does not immerse. The treated alumina immerses easily in water. The proposed structures give a reasonable explanation of this observation. The surface isoelectric point could be an important factor in determining the orientation of the silane, especially the silane layers in the immediate vicinity of the oxide surfaces.

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